

From Greener growth to sufficiency: modeling alternative global sustainability pathways

Abstract

This study quantifies two contrasting global sustainability transition scenarios—FST1: Greener Growth and FST5: Sufficiency Economies—using the MORDRED system dynamics model. While both scenarios pursue high levels of decarbonization without relying on speculative technologies, they embody distinct paradigms: FST1 prioritizes economic growth through green technology and efficiency improvements, whereas FST5 centers on sufficiency, redistribution, and social well-being within ecological limits. The quantitative simulations generate demographic, economic, and biophysical trajectories that complement their qualitative storylines, allowing a plausibility assessment of each transition pathway. Results show that FST1 achieves rapid technological decarbonization but remains constrained by resource and land scarcity, resulting in persistent inequalities and a failure to achieve international climate goals. In contrast, FST5 achieves strong convergence in consumption and mortality rates across regions and classes, stabilizing global warming at 1.9 °C by 2100 while reducing material and water extraction as well as pressures on land systems. At the same time, strong decarbonization increases the renewable sector's share of global resource extraction. Both scenarios appear stable beyond the end of the qualitative storyline in 2075, although the greater level of environmental pressure and inequality in FST1 pose mid- and long-term risks for its stability. Sensitivity analyses demonstrate that scenario plausibility depends on assumptions about climate sensitivity as well as land and labor productivity growth. Overall, this study underscores the importance of integrating qualitative narratives with quantitative modeling to explore plausible global transformation pathways and highlights that sufficiency-oriented transitions may offer more robust sustainability outcomes than growth-oriented ones.

Keywords

Integrated assessment modeling, global environmental scenarios, sustainability transitions, convergence, green growth, decarbonization

1. Introduction

Meeting global climate and sustainability objectives requires profound societal transformations and ambitious policy interventions that break with ‘business-as-usual’ practices, although concrete transition pathways remain contested (Köhler et al., 2019; Scoones et al., 2020; Wiedmann et al., 2020). Sustainability transitions have been linked to Green economies in both the Global North and South (Brown et al., 2014; Hochstetler, 2025; Lederer et al., 2018) as well as to the development of a circular economy (Abunyewah et al., 2023; Fetanat et al., 2021; Flynn et al., 2019), but also to more radical post-growth or degrowth transitions emphasizing the need to reduce consumption inequality and to overcome the ‘growth paradigm’ (Hickel, 2019; Kallis et al., 2025; Schmelzer, 2017).

Debates about sustainability transitions can be informed and enriched by the development of global environmental scenarios that provide visions for desirable futures but also identify socio-economic and biophysical risks within the scenario space (Juri et al., 2025; Msangi, 2013; Pereira et al., 2021; Wilkinson & Mangalagiu, 2012). Ideally, qualitative and quantitative approaches should complement and inform each other through iterative feedbacks, resulting in scenarios rich in narrative detail and supported by quantitative modeling (Alcamo, 2008). In practice, however, modeling and time constraints often lead to scenario exercises that focus predominantly on either storyline creation or model development.

For instance, many quantitative modeling studies of low-demand or sufficiency transitions lack the narrative context provided by detailed storylines that situate modeled measures within coherent and plausible socio-political trajectories (Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020; Wiese, Taillard, et al., 2024; Wiese, Zell-Ziegler, et al., 2024). Moreover, scenario studies with a quantitative component often embody a ‘continuity bias’ (Raskin & Swart, 2020) characterized by the absence of transformative structural changes in the economic, political, and cultural realms that deviate from the status quo (Lauer et al., 2024). For example, strong climate mitigation pathways based on the Low Energy Demand (LED) scenario (Grubler et al., 2018) or SSP2 (Van Vuuren et al., 2018) do not engage with the systemic politico-economic and cultural preconditions that would render the modeled policies feasible. Global sustainability scenarios featuring strong and rapid convergence between the Global North and South toward energy levels compatible with meeting basic human needs remain underexplored (Hickel & Slamersak, 2022). Likewise, systematic model-based comparisons of radically different global-scale transformation pathways and policies have yet to be conducted.

Conversely, many qualitative scenarios reflecting more radical approaches to sustainability are characterized by absent or insufficient quantification (Durán et al., 2023; Otero et al., 2020; Sessa & Ricci, 2014), partly due to the limited capacity of existing integrated assessment models (IAMs) to represent radical systemic change. As a result, their concrete implications for material flows, inequality, and environmental outcomes remain invisible.

Further examples for qualitatively rich scenarios lacking a model-based quantitative exploration are the six recently developed ‘fast sustainability transition scenarios’ (FSTs) (Lauer et al., 2025), which narrate alternative sustainability transformation pathways based on competing socio-economic paradigms and approaches to addressing global socio-economic and environmental challenges, including strong convergence and relocalization as well as eco-socialist and green capitalist growth strategies.

This article aims to complement the FST development by quantifying two of the six FSTs (‘FST1 – Greener Growth’ and ‘FST5 – Sufficiency Economies’) using a recently developed IAM. The

quantification exercise serves four purposes. First, to enrich the qualitative scenario content with a quantitative dimension that illustrates the rate and scale of the envisioned changes. Second, to assess the extent to which the simulated quantitative dynamics align with the scenario storylines and, where relevant, to uncover unexpected dynamics or contradictions between the qualitative and quantitative versions. Third, to compare projected developments in social, economic, and environmental systems across two scenarios featuring transformative changes grounded in distinct sustainability approaches. Finally, to explore how variations in boundary conditions affect simulation results, thereby narrowing the parameter range within which quantitative dynamics align with qualitative scenario content, enabling a plausibility assessment of both scenarios.

2. Methods

2.1. Scenario and model description

FST1 and FST5 are two of six global sustainability scenarios describing potential changes in world order, cultural hegemony, (geo)political alliances and global modes of production that align to form global societal transition pathways spanning several decades. We selected the scenarios because they represent fundamentally different approaches to solving the ‘sustainability conundrum’. Although both aim to achieve greater social, environmental, and economic sustainability throughout the 21st century, in cases of conflict between these goals, FST1 prioritizes economic growth over environmental and social objectives, whereas in FST5, well-being—linked to the notion of ‘sufficiency’—is given the highest political priority.

In FST1, by the end of the 2020s, a new historical bloc emerges that successfully advances a global ‘green growth’ agenda, which becomes mainstreamed into economic and social policies with the support of international institutions, civil society, and intellectuals. While the development of green technological innovation is promoted, less attention is paid to social welfare and inequality. Conversely, in FST5, by the late 2020s, a global movement grounded in strong ecological and social values persuades a group of states to advocate for the establishment of a Planetary Confederation to fundamentally transform the global economic system and decisively address socio-environmental challenges, focusing particularly on basic human needs and sufficiency in consumption.

The complete storylines, which narrate power struggles among social actors, shifts in public discourse, and the implementation of diverse sustainability policies, are detailed in Lauer et al (2025).

The model used to quantify FST1 and FST5 is called MORDRED (Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development). MORDRED is an environmentally and socially extended input-output (IO) model coupled with a demographic model and a climate model, reflecting the growing interest in linking IAM and IO modeling approaches (Lefèvre, 2024; Malik & Schaeffer, 2024). The model was developed to portray non-linear global environmental futures characterized by historical discontinuities in economic growth and demographic developments, as well as scenarios of strong redistribution between and within societies. MORDRED’s subcomponents, structure, and data sources are described in detail in the model documentation (Lauer & Llases, 2025).

The model’s components represent and project future developments across different systems at the global level. The evolution of the world population results from changes in mortality and

fertility rates across three world regions and 20 age cohorts, which are driven by individuals' per capita consumption levels and by public per capita expenditures on health and education. These variables depend on both the region of residence and the individual's social class. At the beginning of each model simulation, the world region 'center'—comprising high-income countries—has the highest per capita health and education expenditures, followed by the 'semiperiphery', consisting of upper-middle-income countries, and the 'periphery', which aggregates all low- and lower-middle-income countries. Within each region, the population fully participating in the global economy is divided into three segments: the richest 20%, the poorest 30%, and the remaining 50%, constituting the middle class. Exogenous scenario assumptions determine how the global distribution of economic consumption goods evolves over the simulation period, enabling the modeling of economic convergence and divergence. Thus, MORDRED can represent different socio-economic groups and inequalities, as well as various forms of distributional justice—an important step toward incorporating justice considerations into IAMs (Low et al., 2025).

Global economic production is represented through Leontief production functions and disaggregated into 25 sectors listed in the Supplementary Material (SM). This sectoral disaggregation allows for the projection of scenario-based developments across different energy sectors, including fossil fuels, biomass, hydropower, solar PV, wind, nuclear, and fossil electricity.

MORDRED's environmental modules project changes in the global climate and land systems and also track the evolution of various forms of air, soil, and water pollution. Additionally, the model converts the economic output of the mining sector into biophysical quantities of extracted materials, including several key minerals for the energy (Owen et al., 2022; Valero et al., 2018).

Importantly, the model incorporates a set of linkages between variables that may constrain economic growth. These constraints operate through several channels. First, labor scarcity arises when the demand for labor hours exceeds the maximum labor supply, which depends on the size of the global working-age population. Second, land scarcity occurs when the demand for specific land types surpasses their available supply. Third, fossil energy scarcity results from the progressive depletion of fossil fuel reserves, ultimately limiting the amount of extractable energy resources per unit of time and increasing extraction costs. Fourth, climate-related damages affect economic performance by reducing the availability and productivity of labor and land, as well as diminishing the capital stock. In addition, production in any sector may decline if the demand for intermediate goods required in the production process cannot be met.

The structure of MORDRED allows scenario developers to selectively activate or deactivate policies, feedback mechanisms, or entire submodules. Depending on the scenario, exogenous parameters can be modified, and new parameters can be added to simulate the effects of different policies—for example, population policies or changes in government expenditure.

Using a single model to quantify both scenarios not only simplifies parameterization and simulation but also enhances the comparability of results. Consequently, differences in the development of key variables arise exclusively from differences in scenario parameter assumptions based on their respective storylines, rather than from differences in model structure.

2.2. Scenario parametrization

To quantify the FST1 and FST5 storylines, we use the translation protocol outlined in Lauer et al. (2025), which consists of a series of scenario objectives pursued to different degrees in each FST. In every scenario, each objective is assigned a level ranging from 0, indicating that the objective is not pursued, to 4, indicating that it is strongly pursued. Consequently, the main part of the parametrization process consisted of identifying which scenario objectives could be represented in MORDRED and assigning the relevant variables numerical values that reflect the indicated level. In this way, the qualitative differences between FST1 and FST5 were ‘translated’ into quantitative differences.

When determining the concrete numerical values, we sought to balance two goals: selecting values that reproduce the developments described in the storylines, and avoiding rates of change that would appear implausible or unfeasible. As a certain degree of subjectivity and uncertainty is unavoidable in this process, all parametrized scenario variables for FST1 and FST5 are enumerated in Table 1, allowing researchers to replicate the simulations using other models and/or alternative rates of change for the variables.

The SM includes the numerical values for the main model variables, many of which depend on the quantified scenario objectives (Table 1). For the remaining model variables, MORDRED’s default values were adopted. The only exception is the model parameter regulating the evolution of different greenhouse gas (GHG) intensities, including CO₂ from non-combustion processes, CH₄, N₂O, SF₆, HFC and PFC. Since this type of intensity is not listed among in the scenario objectives, we include it in Table 1 as an additional variable.

Following the storylines, we set the beginning of the global societal transition in 2029. The preceding decade (2019–2029) is assumed to represent a ‘business-as-usual’ (BAU) period, marked by limited political effort in the social, environmental, economic, and technological spheres, alongside high consumption demands across all social classes. Therefore, technological and consumption parameters during ‘BAU’ are defined separately and are overwritten by the parameters corresponding to FST1 and FST5 from 2029 onwards. Although the narratives only cover the period until 2075, we simulate them until 2100 to assess their stability beyond the temporal end of the storyline.

Rather than focusing on the projection of future changes within an isolated subsystem of the world, we are interested in the development of the world system as a whole, including interactions and feedback effects between human and natural systems and their impacts on variables featured in FST1 and FST5. Accordingly, all interlinkages and feedback mechanisms between model variables are activated during the simulations.

Scenario objectives	FST1	Quantification	FST5	Quantification
Scale of economic/transformation activities				
Increase scale of economic activities	4	<i>Consumption growth rates of 1% (center) to 2.5% (periphery).</i>	0	<i>Consumption growth rates of 1% (center) to 2.5% (periphery) until 2029.</i>
Decrease scale of economic activities	0	<i>Growth rates only become negative as a consequence of biophysical limits to growth.</i>	3	<i>Consumption decreases and converges to 7,500 (2019-)€ between 2029 and 2039.</i>
Reduce size of human population	0	<i>Human population only drops as a result of increased mortality rates.</i>	1	<i>Birth rate multiplier of 0.7 for all regions.</i>

Adapt scale of economic activity to well-being requirements	1	Target growth of poorest social classes and regions assumed to represent well-being requirements.	4	Target consumption level assumed to represent well-being requirements.
Render scale of economy compatible with E&M flows of bioregion	No representation of regional E&M flows			
Increase military & security forces	2	Shift 10% of government expenditures on services (sector 7, including public administration and defense) to education (sector 22) and health (sector 23).	0	-
Decrease military & security forces	0	-	3	Shift 15% of government expenditures from sector 7 to 22 and 23.
Average 'Earth intensity' of economic activities (depends on sectoral composition and technologies)				
Reduce fossil fuel intensity	4	100% greening of electricity, substitution of 60% of fossil energy with green electricity, shift of 50% of remaining fossil energy demands to bioenergy.	4	100% greening of electricity, substitution of 40% of fossil energy with green electricity, shift 60% of remaining fossil energy demands to bioenergy.
Reduce GHG emission intensity	2	Emission intensity of CH ₄ , N ₂ O, SF ₆ , HFC, PFC and non-combustion related CO ₂ reduced by 35%.	2	Emission intensity of CH ₄ , N ₂ O, SF ₆ , HFC, PFC and non-combustion related CO ₂ reduced by 35%.
Reduce energy intensity	3	Process efficiency and efficiency gains from electrification.	4	Higher process efficiency due to higher labor intensity (labor dedicated to the optimization of processes) and higher efficiency gains from electrification (due to lower share of electrification).
Reduce land intensity	2	World adopts the productivity levels that the center held in 2019 for the agriculture and forest sectors, contained in sector 1 & 2; land intensity of renewable electricity technologies improves by 30%; land intensity of biomass energy improves by the same rate as the average of agriculture and forest land.	2	World adopts productivity levels of the center for sector 1 & 2; land intensity of renewable electricity technologies improves by 30%; land intensity of biomass energy improves by the same rate as the average of agriculture and forest land.
Reduce mineral intensity	1	10% reduction in the inputs from sector 4 (mining) in A matrix.	2	20% reduction in the inputs from sector 4 in A matrix.
Reduce biomass intensity	1	10% reduction in the inputs from sector 2 (biomass) in A matrix.	0	-
Reduce water intensity	0	-	2	20% reduction in water intensity.
'Circularity' of economy (duration of materials in economic sphere)				
Increase product use duration	0	-	4	Multiply input coefficients in A matrix by 0.25 for sectors 5, 11, 7, 21 (industry, manufacturing, services and transport) to

				<i>represent a 4-fold increase in product duration and use.</i>
Increase reuse of water, biomass and mineral based products	0	-	4	<i>Water intensity of industries and households reduced by 50%, inputs from sector 2 and 4 in A matrix reduced by 50%.</i>
Increase recycling of materials (minerals)	1	<i>10% reduction in the inputs from sector 4 in A matrix.</i>	3	<i>25% reduction in the inputs from sector 4 in A matrix.</i>
Labor/Capital-intensity				
Increase labor intensity in production process	0	<i>Strong labor intensity decline to 0.8 times the sectoral labor intensities held by the Center in 2019.</i>	4	<i>Increase of initial global average values by 10%.</i>
Increase capital intensity in production process	4	<i>Capital intensity increases by 30%.</i>	0	<i>Constant capital intensity.</i>
Distribution of consumption goods				
Reduce inequalities in consumption /unequal access to consumption goods	0	-	4	<i>Complete elimination of inter- and intraregional inequality, i.e. complete convergence in access to consumption goods.</i>
Aim at need-based allocation of consumption goods	<i>No representation of needs in model.</i>			
Control of productive capacity / the development of productive forces				
Strengthen individual decisions about production	<i>Model does not distinguish between different types of ownership, decision-making and/or ways of production.</i>			
Strengthen collective decisions about production				
Decrease inequality in (private or collective) ownership of means of production				

Table 1: Quantification of FST1 and FST5 storylines, following the translation protocol outlined in Lauer et al. (2025). All changes refer to 2100 as target year. The numbers and names of the economic sector in MORDRED are contained in the SM.

Finally, to test to which extent key model dynamics differ when important boundary conditions are altered, we conducted three additional simulations for both FST scenarios. In each additional simulation, certain scenario parameters were modified.

In the first scenario variation (SV1), which is simulated for both FST1 and FST5, we reduced non-combustion-related GHG intensities by only 10% and increased the sensitivity of the climate system to anthropogenic pressure—specifically by increasing the equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS) by 10% and assuming a higher sensitivity of natural CH₄ emissions and of carbon uptake by biomass from the atmosphere to temperature changes (cf. Kaufhold et al., 2025).

In SV2, also simulated for both FST1 and FST5, the reduction in the land intensity of renewable energy sectors is set to 10% by 2100, i.e. it is assumed that only limited land-use savings can be achieved in renewable energy generation without reducing technological performance (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2017).

SV3 differs between FST1 and FST5. For FST1, we assess the consequences of lower demand for land, resulting from both reduced land intensities and a lower reliance on biomass-based renewable energy. Compared to the ‘default’ FST1 run, the target land intensity in 2100 is reduced by 50% for all non-energy-related land uses. Additionally, it is assumed that only 5% of

non-electric fossil energy is substituted by biomass. For FST5, SV3 explores the effects of a greater reduction in labor productivity on scenario outcomes. Accordingly, the global average sectoral labor intensities are set to increase by 50% by 2100.

Scenario variation	FST1	FST5
SV1	Higher climate sensitivity and less GHG intensity reductions	
SV2	Lower reductions in the land intensity of renewable energy sectors	
SV3	Less pressure on land	More pressure on labor

Table 2: Overview of additional scenario simulations.

3. Results

3.1. FST1: Greener growth

The main economic and socio-demographic changes during the simulation are shown in Fig. 1 while key developments in the biophysical domain are presented in Fig. 2. During the *Greener Growth* scenario, global economic activity continues to expand throughout the 21st century. World output increases by 50% between 2030 and 2100, while the global capital stock nearly doubles over the same period. However, land scarcity constrains economic expansion: compared to a scenario assuming infinite land availability (grey dashed line in Fig. 1a), economic growth in FST1 is considerably lower. By 2075, output in the unlimited-land scenario is almost 1.6 times higher than in FST1.

The increase in output is linked to growing final demand components. The largest component by far is household (private) consumption, followed by gross fixed capital formation and government (public) consumption. Under *Greener Growth*, both private and public consumption rise significantly during the 21st century, although their growth slows in the second half of the simulation. Thus, between 2060 and 2100, total household consumption increases by only 7 trillion 2019-€, compared to an increase of more than 23 trillion € between 2020 and 2060, rising from €44.3 trillion to €67.5 trillion. Global public consumption grows by 6 trillion € in the first half of the simulation, but only 1 trillion € in the second, from 19 to 20 trillion €.

Conversely, due to the increasing capital intensity of production and higher depreciation rates from climate-related damages, investment rises almost linearly throughout the entire simulation, reaching 37.6 trillion €/year at the end of the storyline and 45.5 trillion €/year by 2100. The expansion of capital stock and investment is mirrored in industrial output, which grows by 11.2 trillion € between 2029 and 2075, compared to 4.7, 3.3, and 2.2 trillion € in the food, health, and education sectors, respectively. Even in relative terms, industry exhibits the highest growth rates, reflecting FST1's focus on capital accumulation rather than on the development of food, health, and education provisioning systems.

During the transition period (2029–2075), global average per capita consumption rises moderately from 6,859 €/year to 8,097 €/year, reaching 9,152 €/year by 2100. All classes in the center, as well as the richest 20 % of the semiperiphery, remain above the global average throughout the simulation, while the poorer 80 % of the semiperiphery and periphery never reach it. The top 20 % in the periphery, however, grow rapidly and reach the global average

around 2040 (Fig. 1f). In 2075, the average regional consumption in the center is still three times as high as the global average, converges towards the global level in the semiperiphery, and remains below the global average in the periphery although the gap narrows substantially toward the end of the simulation.

The large population size of the poorest 80% of the semiperiphery and periphery explains the difference between the global average and high consumption levels in the center. Rising consumption across all classes reflects the universal aspiration for continuous consumption growth depicted in the FST1 storyline. However, a peak and subsequent decline in consumption can be observed among the center's classes (Fig. 1f), signaling an involuntary break with historical trends and political ambitions. The richest class of the center does not exceed 50,000 per capita consumption per year. After the final year of the storyline, per capita consumption continues to rise in the semiperiphery and periphery but declines gradually in the center (Fig. 1d-f), implying a geopolitical shift not mentioned in the qualitative storyline.

The FST1 storyline also lacks explicit demographic information, which the quantification provides. Model results show that global population peaks around mid-century at 8.8 billion, then begins to decline, reaching 8.7 billion by 2075—slightly above the 8.3 billion observed at the start of the global transition in 2029. Driven by the development trajectory, global birth rates fall sharply, especially outside the center, leading to a moderate decline in the semiperiphery's population and stabilization in the periphery by 2075 (Fig. 1g). The mortality rate index—calculated for each age group relative to the semiperiphery's base-year value (set to 1)—is projected to decrease for all age cohorts in the semiperiphery and periphery, and to remain constant in the center. Child mortality declines significantly, while progress among older populations is more limited (Fig. 1h & i). Nevertheless, regional disparities persist, reflecting the scenario's reliance on economic development rather than global redistribution, which proves insufficient to eliminate inequalities in life expectancy.

Fig. 1: Evolution of a) world output (light blue), world output without land restrictions on growth (dashed grey line) and total capital stock (dark blue); b) annual investment (dark green), private consumption (light blue) and public consumption (dark blue); c) output of the industry (light green), food (dark green), education (light blue) and health (dark blue) sector; d) average per capita consumption of the world (grey), the center (light blue), the richest 20% (dark blue), the poorest 30% (light green) and the middle class of the center (dark green); e) average per capita consumption of the world (grey), the semiperiphery (light blue), the richest 20% (dark blue), the poorest 30% (light green) and the middle class of the semiperiphery (dark green); f) average per capita consumption of the world (grey), the periphery (light blue), the richest 20% (dark blue), the poorest 30% (light green) and the middle class of the periphery (dark green); g) world population (dark blue), population in the center (light green), semiperiphery (light blue) and periphery (dark green); h) child mortality index for the center (light green), semiperiphery (light blue) and periphery (dark green); i) mortality index (people aged 70 to 74) for the center (light green), semiperiphery (light blue) and periphery (dark green) in the FST1 scenario.

The political efforts to promote the decarbonization of the global economy in FST1 are mirrored in a continuous and fast reduction of total GHG emissions caused by the global sustainability transition (Fig. 2d). Global GHG emissions peak at 54.7 Gt in 2030 and then decline steadily. From 2060 onward, declining population further accelerates the reduction. By 2075, GHG emissions have been reduced by 37% compared to 2030, and by 2100 are more than 50 % below 2019 levels.

The reduction is primarily driven by falling CO₂ emissions (Fig. 2a). Anthropogenic CH₄ emissions peak with the onset of the transition and decline moderately during the simulation (Fig. 2b), while N₂O emissions only peak around 2060 (Fig. 2c). However, despite these reductions, the change of global average temperature compared to the pre-industrial period crosses the 2 °C threshold in 2045, reaching 2.4 °C by 2075 and 2.6 °C by 2100 (Fig. 2e).

Notably, emissions decline despite continuous growth in total energy use, reflecting substantial progress in decarbonization. This is enabled by a sharp reduction in fossil energy use, including the complete phaseout of fossil-based electricity by 2100, and a strong expansion of electric and non-electric renewables (Fig. 2j-l), consistent with the FST1 narrative of large-scale investment in green technologies.

However, the transition involves significant increases in mineral demand. Due to the strong increase in renewable electricity, copper extraction rises significantly during the simulation. By 2100, one-third of global copper output serves the renewable energy sector (Fig. 2g). Similar patterns occur for other minerals critical to the energy transition. Bulk materials such as iron and sand also increase steadily, while fossil resources used as industrial feedstocks continue to rise modestly (Fig. 2i). Industrial blue water use more than doubles between 2029 and 2075 (Fig. 2h), and green water use also increases, suggesting that freshwater consumption may exceed ecological thresholds (Rockström et al., 2009). These trends indicate a neglect of non-fossil-fuel-related environmental pressures in the FST1 development paradigm.

Last, technological changes in FST1 reshape global land systems. Due to land-use pressures, primary forest area declines by 80 % over the simulation while land devoted to built infrastructure and energy generation expands sharply, occupying 3.4 % and 9 %, respectively, of global habitable land by 2075 (Fig. 2f). Importantly, the slow-down of economic growth is caused by an excessive demand for land to generate renewable energies which stems from the effort to substitute fossil fuels with biomass-based energy, and which cannot be satisfied fast enough.

Fig. 2: Evolution of a) anthropogenic CO₂ emissions without land use change emissions; b) CH₄ emissions; c) N₂O emissions; d) total GHG emissions without land use change per year; e) global average temperature change compared to 1850; f) share of primary forest (dark green), land used for energy generation (light green), and infrastructure (blue) in total habitable land area; g) annual copper extraction for renewable energy technologies (light blue) and for the rest of economic production (dark blue); h) annual industrial blue water consumption; i) final non-energy use of oil (dark green), gas (blue) and coal (light green); j) final (non-electric) energy from biomass (dark blue) and electric energy (light blue); k) final (non-electric) energy from oil (dark green), gas (blue), coal (light green); l) fossil fuel- (grey), hydro- (dark blue), nuclear- (light green), solar PV- (dark green) and wind-based (light blue) electricity in the FST1 scenario.

Hence, compared to the storyline, the quantitative scenario simulation yields some additional insights on ‘FST1 – greener growth’, notably demographic developments, such as changes in population size and mortality, and projections of biophysical variables enabling a more precise assessment of environmental impacts. Some aspects, however, remain beyond the model’s scope, including green trade, speculative technologies (e.g., carbon capture, nuclear fusion), and interregional financial flows.

Overall, the simulation results confirm key shortcomings of the FST1 approach to the sustainability conundrum, as identified in the storyline: higher material extraction rates and increased risks of ecological distribution conflicts (Martinez-Alier, 2003, 2004) due to expanding commodity frontiers, alongside failure to meet the Paris Agreement and rising climate-related damages impacting the food sector. Thus, the title of FST1 is pertinent: Grows becomes greener, especially in terms of decarbonization, yet not green enough to prevent intensifying anthropogenic pressure on planetary systems.

While the storyline does not specify the rate of economic growth, the simulations indicate continued, though slower, expansion of the world economy during the transition, constrained by

land scarcity linked to bioenergy expansion. This underscores the growing conflict between accumulation and the ecological imperative in FST1.

On the social side, the simulations confirm FST1's narrative of limited economic convergence. However, the 'burden' of slower economic growth in the simulation is shared between the classes of the semiperiphery and periphery that face a slower decline of poverty, and the classes of the center, that see their consumption levels decline in absolute terms. Thus, in our simulation the weakening of pro-labor policies and unemployment support mentioned in the FST1 storyline mainly affects poorer classes of the center. Since the storyline does not specify how relative losses in growth are distributed across regions, alternative quantifications remain conceivable in which consumption stagnates or declines for poorer classes outside the center, while the center continues to expand.

3.2. FST5: Sufficiency economies

In the quantified version of FST5, world output grows to 170 trillion € at the start of the global transition, then declines by 30% and during the next decades increases slowly to reach a second peak at 139 trillion € in 2058. During the second half of the simulation output declines slowly, reaching 109 trillion € by 2075 and 72 trillion € by 2100 (Fig. 3a). Although capital intensity is assumed to remain constant, due to endogenous economic developments that are affected by increasing climate damages and by the growth in relatively capital-intensive sectors, the economic-wide capital-stock-to-output ratio increases moderately during the scenario while the development of total capital stock fluctuates with changing output. As a result of the general decrease in economic activity in FST5, investment approximates public consumption during the transition and by the end of the storyline has even dropped below the public consumption level (Fig. 3b). Meanwhile, global private consumption reaches a peak in 2058 at 59 trillion € and subsequently declines to 52 trillion by 2075 and 38 trillion € by 2100.

The lower demand for capital goods during the transition drives reductions in the output of the industrial sector. Output in all four sectors, depicted in Fig. 3c, peaks between 2055 and 2060 at low levels that do not surpass 12.6 trillion €/year. By 2100, with 6.9 trillion, the output in the food sector is the highest among the four sectors, followed by health sector. After its peak, the industrial sector's output declines faster compared to the other sectors, and by 2100, is only marginally higher than the education sector's output. These changes indicate the relative importance of food, health and education in FST5 compared to industrial development.

Due to global redistribution policies rapid convergence between classes to the global average consumption can be observed in all world regions (Fig. 3d-f). The class that experiences the greatest consumption cuts in absolute terms is the richest class of the center whose consumption drops from almost 45,000 €/year in 2029 to 5,243 €/year in 2033. Between 2029 and 2039 the richest class of the semiperiphery as well as the remaining classes of the center lose a significant share of their consumption budget while the poorer classes of the semiperiphery and especially the periphery see their consumption grow at very high rates. As a result of global transition policies, between 2029 and 2055 the per capita consumption of the poorest 30% of the semiperiphery and periphery increases almost 5 and more than 6.5 times, respectively. The target per capita consumption of 7,500 €/year is reached in 2056; by 2059, global per capita consumption has reached 7,676 €/year. This value is maintained until the end of the simulation period.

The consumption reduction of richer classes to levels below the target level, as well as the multiple peaks and small instabilities observed in Fig. 3a-c at the end of the 2020s, during the

early years of the 2030s and at the end of the 2050s are caused by labor and land scarcity that constrains the desired economic development in FST5. Excessive land and labor demand lead to a lower growth of the poorest class of the periphery, which, in combination with complete and fast consumption convergence, results in global consumption levels lower than the 7,500 € target. Since household consumption influences all other relevant economic variables, e.g. public consumption, investment and output, the impacts of scarcity are also observable in the latter. Thus, a more plausible dynamic would show partial convergence during the first three decades of the transition, preventing the consumption of richer classes from falling below the €7,500 target, while allowing poorer classes to gradually approach the target consumption level. However, an undesired side effect of this quantification would be an increase of overall anthropogenic pressure on planetary systems and a reduction in climate mitigation (Fig. 4).

Due to the population policy implemented in FST5, world population already peaks in 2033 and afterwards declines to 6.78 billion people by the end of the storyline. The periphery is the only world region where population continues to grow despite the population policy. However, this trend is reversed in 2049. As a result of these demographic developments, in 2075 the population of the periphery is 5 times as large as the population of the center, and more than 1.5 times as large as the population in the semiperiphery (Fig. 3g). Combined with the convergence in per capita consumption this implies a much higher weight of the periphery in the 'Planetary Confederation' of FST5. Thus, countries of these world region would likely no longer be 'peripheral' to the global economy but become its central driving force.

Mortality rates in all age groups and regions converge to a global value by 2039, which is significantly lower than initial mortality in the semiperiphery and periphery but slightly higher than initial mortality levels in the center for child mortality (Fig. 3h), and considerably higher than the initial center-values for the mortality of the older population (aged 70 to 74 years in Fig. 3i). This points to the importance of an analysis disaggregated not only by class but also by age when studying the effects of economic development on mortality and fertility.

Fig. 3: Evolution of a) world output (purple) and total capital stock (pink) (dashed line: world output without land restrictions); b) annual investment (red), private consumption (pink) and public consumption (purple); c) output of the industry (orange), food (red), education (pink) and health (purple) sector; d) average per capita consumption of the world (black), the center (pink), the richest 20% of the center (purple), the poorest 30% of the center (orange) and the middle class of the center (red); e) average per capita consumption of the world (black), the semiperiphery (pink), the richest 20% (purple), the poorest 30% (orange) and the middle class of the semiperiphery (red); f) average per capita consumption of the world (black), the periphery (pink), the richest 20% (purple), the poorest 30% (orange) and the middle class of the periphery (red); g) world population (purple), population in the center (orange), semiperiphery (pink) and periphery (red); h) child mortality index for the center (orange), semiperiphery (pink) and periphery (red); i) mortality index (people aged 70 to 74) for the center (orange), semiperiphery (pink) and periphery (red) in the FST5 scenario.

During the first 10 years of the global sustainability transition in FST5 total GHG emissions fall drastically. The reduction slows down between 2040 and 2060 and accelerates again during the second half of the simulation period (Fig. 4d). This dynamic is driven mostly by global CO₂ emissions (Fig. 4a) and is reinforced by CH₄ and N₂O emissions which start to fall from 2060 onwards, driven especially by a decline in the food sector's output, as well as falling GHG emission intensities (Fig. 4b-c).

The statement in the FST5 storyline that the transition to a Planetary Confederation occurs too late to reach the 1.5 °C climate goal is confirmed in the simulation (Fig. 4e). Nevertheless, it is a remarkable achievement of FST5 to keep global warming below 2 °C during the entire simulation period: The global sustainability transition manages to slow down the increase in global average temperatures, and consequently, between 2029 and 2075 global average temperature only increases by 0.5 °C. By 2100 the world is 1.88°C warmer than in the pre-industrial (1850) reference period. Although this degree of warming already risks triggering multiple climate tipping points (Armstrong McKay et al., 2022) and is linked to significant climate-induced damages, adaptation possibilities are much higher than in scenarios with higher levels of climate change (cf. IPCC, 2022)

The transition manages to leave the extent of the world's primary forests unchanged, which is partly explained by the low peaks in the land shares human-built infrastructure and land used for energy generation (Fig. 4f). Additionally, the growth in industrial blue water consumption slows down during the transition and eventually global blue water extraction declines. By 2100, industrial blue water consumption is projected to be 48% lower than in 2019 (Fig. 4h). The final energy use of fossil resources declines steeply during the entire transition period while renewable electricity grows to reach 20.9 EJ, 21 EJ and 13.1 EJ in 2075 for wind, solar PV and hydropower, respectively (Fig. 4k & l). By 2100, fossil-based electricity has disappeared, while the non-electric energetic use of coal, gas and oil has been reduced by 93% compared to the start of the transition. The growth in electric- and non-electric energy does not offset the degrowth of energetic fossil resource use, resulting in a strong net reduction of energy use in FST5.

The growth in renewables compared with the general degrowth in the economy and the assumed improvements in material intensity and material recycling leads to a strong increase in material extraction for the renewable sector and a simultaneous strong decline in material extraction for the rest of the economy. For example, by 2100, half of the total copper production is dedicated to the maintenance of the renewable electricity infrastructure (Fig. 4g).

At the same time, the use of fossil resources as material feedstock decreases, although at a lower rate compared to reductions in fossil fuel combustion (Fig. 4i). By 2075, the world still relies on fossil resource extraction to use the equivalent of 12.7 EJ of oil, 3.7 EJ of gas and 0.9 EJ of coal in industrial processes. The small amount of coal used as industrial feedstock, coupled with the reduction of coal in the electricity sector points to a strong loss of significance of the coal sector in FST5.

Fig. 4: Evolution of a) anthropogenic CO₂ emissions without land use change emissions; b) CH₄ emissions; c) N₂O emissions; d) total GHG emissions without land use change per year; e) global average temperature change compared to 1850; f) share of primary forest (red), land used for energy generation (orange), and infrastructure (pink) in total habitable land area; g) annual copper extraction for renewable energy technologies (purple) and for the rest of economic production (pink); h) annual industrial blue water consumption; i) final non-energy use of oil (red), gas (pink) and coal (orange); j) final (non-electric) energy from biomass (pink) and electric energy (purple); k) final (non-electric) energy from oil (red), gas (pink), coal (orange); l) fossil fuel- (black), hydro- (purple), nuclear- (orange), solar PV- (red) and wind-based (pink) electricity in the FST5 scenario.

Overall, the simulation outcomes fit the FST5 storyline: The egalitarian distribution of wealth is reflected through strong convergence in household consumption while investment in the model exclusively serves to realize private and public consumption and does not lead to increasing inequalities over time through private capital accumulation. The convergence in living standards and mortality rates is strong and fast, while the extraction of both rare and bulk materials is reduced throughout and beyond the scenario, despite the expansion of the renewable sector. The simulation shows a low but permanent reliance on fossil resources for material uses, as well as GHG emissions and annual material extraction rates greater than zero, which points to the absence of an 'ideal' circular economy with closed material circles.

Nevertheless, some additional insights can be gained from the quantification: First, the climate damages represented in the model, which increase with global average temperature, are not significant enough to pose a threat to economic reproduction during and beyond the FST5 scenario storyline, despite the higher labor productivity in this scenario and the negative impact of global warming on labor productivity (Dasgupta et al., 2021).

Second, temporal land and labor scarcity issues can endanger the feasibility of FST5. In other words, higher land and labor productivities, or at least faster growth rates in the first half of the

simulation, would likely create a smoother development pathway under FST5. The simulation also indicates that fast growth rates in the poorer classes – such as over 20% in the poorest classes at the global level – might pose feasibility problems.

Additionally, the scenario quantification demonstrates that FST5 only works with significant improvements in land productivity because at low consumption levels, food expenses make up a relatively large share of total expenditure. Thus, an increase in consumption will generate a higher demand for land than a similar increase at a higher consumption level. If land productivity improvements do not match the consumption growth of poorer classes, land conversions and the associated loss of biodiversity and increase in GHG emissions become more probable.

Finally, a dynamic that reduces anthropogenic pressure on ecosystems and sustains high levels of climate mitigation beyond 2075 is the continuous population decline, which is not explicitly considered in the FST5 storyline. This demographic trend emerges as an important stabilizing factor in the scenario. With the exception of temporary labor shortages in the first half of the simulation, no significant labor scarcity is observed in the second half, despite the aging population. However, workforce utilization remains high throughout the simulation and increases slowly but steadily over the last four decades, suggesting that long-term stability of FST5 will ultimately require either population stabilization or renewed growth in labor productivity.

3.3. Comparison of FST1 and FST5

Comparing the two scenario simulations we find that FST5 is linked to considerably lower levels of anthropogenic pressure on planetary systems. While FST5 manages to keep global warming below 2°C by 2100, in FST1 none of the climate objectives of the Paris Agreement are reached. Additionally, FST1 has a narrow focus on climate mitigation and ignores other environmental stressors such as water consumption, the material use of fossil resources, material extraction or land use conversion, while in FST5 these variables improve during the scenario. Last, the effect of the presence or absence of limits to growth imposed by the availability of land is much higher in FST1 than in FST5 (compare dashed lines in Fig. 1a and Fig. 3a).

While life expectancy and per capita consumption of the poorest increase in both scenarios, class and territorial inequalities are reduced considerably faster in FST5. Thus, in FST1, the poorest 30% of the periphery live with very low consumption levels throughout and beyond the global transition. At the same time, although the richest classes in the center eventually see their consumption levels decline in both scenarios, the loss in consumption is much more pronounced in FST5.

Once the global-level policies are implemented, both scenarios are stable beyond the final year of the storyline (2075), although the greater level of environmental pressure and inequality in FST1 pose mid- and long-term risks for its stability.

4. Discussion

4.1. Boundary conditions and scenario plausibility

By changing key boundary conditions in the simulations, we can identify which scenario assumptions must hold for the outcomes to resemble the FST storylines. These assumptions can then be evaluated in terms of their plausibility.

For each dimension (economic, social, environmental) we select one key variable for assessment: *output*, because it represents the scale of overall economic activity; *consumption per capita*, because in the model this variable influences life expectancy and serves as an indicator of well-being (at least until a certain consumption level) (Carver & Grimes, 2019; Vollebregt et al., 2024); and *changes in global average temperature*, because they serve as an indicator of anthropogenic pressure on planetary systems.

Simulating the first scenario variation (SV1) we find that more pessimistic assumptions about the climate system's sensitivity lead to higher levels of global warming, lower output due to climate damages, and reduced per capita consumption (Fig. 5a-d). The output loss is significantly greater for FST1 than for FST5, and it causes the consumption of the richest class to fall below their initial level by 2100, while the reduction in consumption of the poorest class further hampers poverty elimination. Because even small changes in the magnitude of global warming visibly alter the scenario outcomes, we conclude that the quantifications—especially for FST1—are sensitive to assumptions about the climate system, and that greater climate sensitivity diminishes the scenarios' long-term stability and renders them less plausible.

In SV2 we observe relatively small deviations from the original scenario outcomes (Fig. 5e-h); these deviations are reduced in FST1 and nearly eliminated in FST5 during the second half of the simulation. Interestingly, this suggests that technological progress in (land) efficiency of renewables has a comparatively minor influence on the feasibility of the scenarios.

For FST1, SV3 diverges notably from the original scenario simulation, with higher outcomes, elevated consumption levels and weak climate mitigation. Despite the substantial improvement in land intensity—which buffers the increasing climate-change-related land damages—growing difficulties in sustaining economic growth become apparent toward the end of the simulation. Since a low level of fossil-bioenergy substitution does not align with the FST1 storyline, and the very high land-intensity improvements required to achieve the same growth rate through biomass-based energy seem difficult to attain (especially given factors that tend to reduce land productivity, such as soil-fertility loss (Cherlet et al., 2018) or forest productivity decline (Mohr et al., 2025)), FST1 appears plausible only under lower-than-desirable growth levels.

For FST5, SV3 demonstrates that the assumed increase in labor intensity in the original quantification represents an upper bound: with lower labor productivity levels, the consumption target of FST5 can no longer be met (Fig. 5o,p). Thus, assuming a stronger increase in labor intensity—as in SV3—reduces the feasibility of FST5.

There are other important boundary conditions that we did not vary in the scenario analyses. These include resource availability, the severity of damages, and impacts of biodiversity loss. Estimates of remaining and accessible fossil resources vary widely (Delannoy et al., 2021; Fricko et al., 2017; Laherrère et al., 2022; Turner, 2008). However, using a medium estimate in our simulations, we find that by 2100 only 74 % of estimated fossil reserves have been extracted in FST1 and only 45 % in FST5. Thus, in sustainability transition scenarios, uncertainty about fossil resources plays a lesser role than in high-emission pathways. Regarding the accessibility of

minerals, comparing the quantities of tin and copper extracted between 2019 and 2100 in FST1 and FST5 with the Ultimately Available Resources (UAR) estimates of Henckens (2021), we find extracted shares of 18 % and 5 % for tin, and 27 % and 8 % for copper, respectively. We conclude that mineral resource availability has a relatively minor impact on scenario plausibility—especially for FST5.

The severity of climate damages was not varied in the scenarios, although they certainly influence development pathways (IPCC, 2022). Nevertheless, since damages evolve nonlinearly, we argue that the question of severity is more central for worst-case climate scenarios, while the transition scenarios modeled here exhibit comparatively moderate temperature rises.

Finally, given that MORDRED does not represent potential effects of declining ecosystem services on economic reproduction the scenario outcomes are likely over-optimistic, especially for FST1 which exhibits higher resource and land pressures.

In general, the rates of change assumed during transitions in FST1 and FST5 are far higher than historical rates of change. However, we maintain that this does not make them implausible, since both scenarios are built on the premise of a substantial change in world order and a reconfiguration of political priorities.

Fig. 5: Evolution of key output variables in scenarios with changed boundary conditions (FST1 = light blue, FST5 = pink), compared to the baseline scenario results (FST1 = dark blue, FST5 = purple. a, e, i, m: total world output; b, f, j, n: global average temperature change compared to 1850; c, g, k, o: consumption per capita of the richest 20% of the center; d, h, l, p: consumption per capita of the poorest 30% of the periphery. a-d) Baseline scenarios compared to scenarios with higher climate sensitivity and less GHG intensity reductions; e-h) Baseline scenarios compared to scenarios with lower reductions in the land intensity of renewable energy sectors; i-l) Baseline compared to a scenario with higher land intensity reductions and lower substitution of fossil energy through bioenergy. m-p) Baseline compared to a scenario with a higher labor intensity increase.

4.2. Policy relevance and future work

Our simulations are not predictions of the future but data-based imagined futures supporting societal and political decision-making and planning (Juri et al., 2025). As we focus on very broad development at the global level, the policy relevance of our work equally is of global character since regional or local policies can be better informed by concrete case-specific modeling studies. Three key policy-relevant insights can be formulated based on the simulation outcomes of FST1 and FST5.

First, the modeling results clearly indicate that FST5 has better chances to meet both environmental and social sustainability goals, namely a slowdown of environmental degradation, the eradication of poverty and the reduction of social inequality. FST1 does not only fail to achieve climate goals but is also characterized by a constant decrease in the workforce utilization rate, pointing at a risk of emerging unemployment issues, which has already been discussed by O'Neill (2020). Thus, our work provides model-based support for those strands in the ongoing debate on sustainability transitions that promote development paradigms and policies similar to those in FST5, such as degrowth, post-growth or steady-state economics (Daly, 2013; Fitzpatrick et al., 2022).

Second, the simulations show that strong reductions of anthropogenic pressure on planetary systems are possible even in the absence of speculative technologies or technological breakthroughs such as negative emission technologies (NETs) or nuclear fusion. However, successful mitigation depends critically on radical convergence, consumption reduction and a series of changes in production processes such as recycling, product reuse etc. Importantly, in the simulation, policy measures are implemented fast and throughout the world. Thus, our scenario study confirms the urgent need to look for radical solutions beyond national boundaries, which in turn, can only be implemented under a changed world order with new institutional 'rules of the game' shaping global economic, political and cultural systems.

Last, the scenario quantification exercise reaffirms the importance of holistic sustainability policies targeting demographic, economic, social, cultural and technological developments, since it is the combination of simultaneous changes in different sub-modules that drive simulation outcomes in both FSTs. For example, the population policy in FST5 significantly contributes to its mitigation success. Likewise, the rapid decarbonization of the economy in both scenarios increases the relative importance of GHG emissions from other sources than fossil fuel combustion, such as N₂O or SF₆ that should be addressed with specific globally harmonized policies.

Our simulations could be refined in future work by integrating more biophysical feedbacks to address the optimistic bias of the simulations, by improving the representation of land-related processes, and by updating the IO data used (Stadler et al., 2018). Equally, multiple FST scenarios, including FST1 and FST5, could be introduced into different IAMs. This would enable comparing the performance of different sustainability paradigms in models other than MORDRED but also would serve to explore differences in outcomes stemming from differences in model structures. Since many IAMs use NETs it can be expected that climate-related results would improve for both FSTs. Additionally, the emission pathways generated by MORDRED could be fed into more sophisticated climate modules to explore possible variations in the level of global warming. Finally, researchers could develop new models that focus on aspects of the FSTs that neither MORDRED nor other existing IAMs can represent, such as ownership structures, decision-making processes in economic production, basic human needs and a need-based allocation of goods (Table 1).

5. Conclusion

In this article, we quantified two global sustainability transition scenarios—FST1: Greener Growth and FST5: Sufficiency Economy—using the MORDRED-IAM. Overall, the scenario outcomes align well with their respective storylines, supporting their plausibility. The

simulations complement the qualitative narratives by generating demographic, consumption, production, and emission pathways. Both scenarios achieve substantial decarbonization without relying on speculative technologies; however, only FST5 limits global warming to below 2 °C. Future research could extend this work by quantifying the remaining FSTs, implementing FST1 and FST5 in other IAMs, and developing new models to explore aspects not covered in this analysis, such as shifts in ownership structures or need-based goods allocation.

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